

A Blockchain Framework for Incentivized Data Sharing in Autonomous Vehicle Networks*

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Abstract—Autonomous vehicles (AVs) continuously generate high-resolution sensor data on road conditions, infrastructure updates, and traffic dynamics. Despite their critical relevance for real-time navigation and urban planning, these datasets remain siloed within manufacturer-specific platforms. To address this problem, we propose a decentralized, blockchain-based framework for secure, real-time data exchange and monetization across diverse vehicle brands and operators. AVs acting as active network participants can submit and validate road events—such as newly detected closures or construction sites—through a modular smart contract system employing dynamic voting thresholds. This dynamic structure adjusts acceptance criteria based on different factors, allowing urgent changes to achieve consensus while quickly minimizing malicious or erroneous reporting. In our model, participants who contribute verified information receive token-based incentives redeemable for operational cost reductions, including charging discounts or parking fees. We validated our approach through a hardhat simulation, implementing the blockchain architecture and smart contracts within an Ethereum-compatible test environment, highlighting the effectiveness of our dynamic voting mechanism and reputation management logic under various scenarios. Simulation results demonstrate our framework’s feasibility, robustness, and responsiveness, underlining its potential as an economically sustainable, secure, and scalable foundation for decentralized AV data marketplaces.

Index Terms—Autonomous Vehicles, Blockchain, Decentralized Framework, Token Incentives, Distributed Validation

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous vehicles (AVs) generate vast, high-resolution datasets through advanced sensor networks—including LiDAR, camera arrays, and radar systems—capturing everything from evolving road conditions to near-instantaneous traffic updates. Although these data are essential for enhancing road safety, optimizing route planning, and guiding infrastructure development, most information remains locked within brand-specific platforms. As a result, AVs from different manufacturers do not benefit from each other’s real-time observations, and public authorities, service providers, and end users miss out on crucial insights for city-wide traffic management, road maintenance, and urban planning. Additionally, modern proprietary navigation platforms typically operate under centralized, closed-source paradigms, offering no direct economic incentives to users for sharing high-precision data and severely limiting data ownership transparency within the provider’s ecosystem.

Blockchain-based architectures have recently been recognized as a promising solution to overcome these limitations, specifically addressing key ITS challenges such as scalability, security, and data integrity. For instance, Das et al. [1] provides a broad overview of blockchain applicability in Intelligent Transportation Systems, detailing benefits in terms of scalability, authentication, confidentiality, and removing single points of failure. However, they do not address economic incentive

mechanisms necessary for cross-brand real-time data sharing. While extensive reviews such as those conducted by Sarwatt et al. [2] and Alherimi et al. [3] have provided comprehensive visions of emerging technologies and their integration, they fail to explicitly tackle the critical need to dismantle barriers between automotive manufacturers, leaving significant room for the specific cross-brand integration this paper aims to address.

Beyond blockchain, recent methodologies employing cryptographic techniques, as demonstrated by Dastagir et al. [4], present sophisticated privacy-preserving schemes based on Non-Interactive Zero Knowledge Proof (NIZKP) and time-based one-time passwords (TOTP). Although their study targets NFT authentication, their approach can be adapted for securing vehicular data in decentralized environments, further confirming the robustness and versatility of cryptographic methods for enhancing privacy in sensitive sensor-data exchanges. Similarly, the servitization models by Leminen et al. [5] illustrate how IoT, Artificial Intelligence algorithms, and smart contracts facilitate new market models enabling digital transformation in autonomous vehicles ecosystems, complementing decentralized frameworks through innovative approaches for monetizing AV-derived data.

To enhance data monetization and equitable revenue distribution, Agarwal et al. [6] propose market design methodologies employing robust pricing and auction mechanisms (Myerson’s payment rule and Multiplicative Weights algorithm combined with Shapley value) to facilitate truthful, fair, and efficient trade of machine learning training datasets. These insights offer valuable directions to optimize fair revenue-sharing mechanisms and incentivize collaborative and economically-sound participation in decentralized marketplaces such as the one this research aims to establish. In parallel, recent interest in Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAOs) has seen applications in vehicular contexts by Yang et al. [7], who present dual-layer DAO models for the Internet of Vehicles environments. Their reputation-weighted voting mitigates token concentration risk; nevertheless, they do not consider mechanisms for real-time, cross-brand monetization of vehicle-generated data. Similarly, Rasool et al. [8] integrate DAO and blockchain in organizational decision-making yet remain limited to corporate structures without addressing vehicle interoperability or real-time sensor-data exchanges between different automotive producers.

Finally, complex multi-chain architectures have emerged, such as the tri-blockchain “TriBoDeS” solution described by Qin et al. [9], which employs distinct chains for identity, road data and trusted snapshots to disseminate hazard information within IoV environments. Although promising, such multi-chain partitioning significantly increases configuration complexity and operational overhead, pointing towards a simplified blockchain approach as a potentially more agile and flexible solution suited to heterogeneous AV industry scenarios involving multiple manufacturers.

Motivated by these considerations and to bridge existing gaps

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in current approaches, we propose a distributed data framework specifically tailored to autonomous vehicles that leverages blockchain-based smart contracts, cryptographic privacy techniques, and token-driven incentives. In this framework, vehicles act as active market participants who upload, validate, buy, and sell sensor information across manufacturer boundaries. Verified contributions are assigned token rewards, redeemable for tangible benefits like charging discounts, reduced parking fees, or toll payments. Crucially, our blockchain-based solution offers transparency, decentralized consensus checks distributed across multiple stakeholders, direct economic incentivization for individual contributors, and eliminates single points of failure typical of traditional centralized models. Moreover, real-time interoperability across diverse manufacturer platforms ensures fair access and fosters sustainable collaboration, significantly enhancing autonomous vehicle data marketplaces' reliability, privacy, and inclusivity.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows: Section II describes the problem, and Section III outlines the System Architecture. Section IV mathematically outlines the dynamic threshold of the considered system, Section V presents the blockchain simulation and Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Autonomous vehicles can collect both static information, such as road infrastructure characteristics and classification, and dynamic phenomena, such as unexpected traffic incidents, temporary road closures, or routine maintenance work. Despite the critical importance of these insights for real-time decision-making and broader traffic management, the data collected often remains confined within proprietary ecosystems belonging to individual manufacturers.

The isolation of data within brand-specific platforms severely limits interoperability and stifles the potential benefits of a more comprehensive, cross-manufacturer data repository. For instance, consider a scenario in which a vehicle navigates what was initially marked as a secondary, paved route in its onboard navigation system yet encounters an unpaved, rough terrain in reality. The AV's sensors detect this mismatch, generating valuable information about the true state of the roadway. However, because this information remains locked within the proprietary system of a single manufacturer, other AVs and stakeholders do not benefit from these real-time observations. When vehicles do not share accurate, up-to-date data about road conditions and ongoing events, critical applications such as route optimization, real-time incident response, and infrastructure maintenance schedules suffer.

A key challenge in addressing these limitations lies in establishing a secure, trust-based mechanism that incentivizes the seamless exchange of vehicular data across multiple stakeholders. Specifically, we aim to address the following elements:

- **Data Provenance and Integrity:** Ensuring confidence in the source and authenticity of shared data, mitigating issues related to falsification and tampering.
- **Owner Privacy:** Preserving the anonymity of vehicle owners and operators, particularly in cases where the data contains sensitive or personally identifiable information.
- **Monetization and Incentives:** Providing economic or operational incentives —such as credits redeemable for charging discounts— that encourage data sharing on a large scale.
- **Real-Time Processing and Scalability:** Facilitating rapid, near-instantaneous transactions in a distributed environ-

ment while accommodating the data throughput requirements of modern sensor systems.

In light of these considerations, the need for a distributed data framework becomes evident. By leveraging blockchain-based architectures, smart contracts, and advanced cryptographic techniques, AV data can be securely exchanged and monetized across brand and platform boundaries.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND MODULAR SMART CONTRACTS

This section presents the proposed system architecture, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The architecture enables AVs from different manufacturers to detect, broadcast, and validate critical environmental changes via a public, permissionless blockchain infrastructure. The core components and interactions are summarized in the following subsections.

Fig. 1. System architecture [10]

A. Overview of the Proposed Workflow

Step 1: Detection of Discrepancy. Vehicle A (shown in orange in Fig. 1) identifies a mismatch between the real-world state of an infrastructure element (e.g., a newly unpaved road or a temporary closure) and the existing information in its onboard navigation system. This discrepancy can arise from *ad hoc* changes (e.g., ongoing construction) or more permanent infrastructural modifications.

Step 2: Broadcast of New Information. Once Vehicle A detects this discrepancy, it encodes the updated information (e.g., the exact location, time, and nature of the change) in a structured JSON object. Our earlier research [11] indicates that implementing a hash-based system for uniquely identifying intersections is feasible. This JSON payload is then submitted to the *smart contract system* (further elaborated in Algorithm 1), triggering a blockchain transaction. This transaction records key metadata such as a timestamp, vehicle pseudonym (to preserve privacy), and event category.

Step 3: Pending State Creation. Upon receiving the transaction, the blockchain-based smart contract appends the new data

to a global dataset in a *pending state*. At this stage, the reported change has no immediate effect on navigation systems; rather, it awaits consensus from other vehicles.

Step 4: Crowd-Sourced Validation. As vehicles **B**, **C**, and **D** traverse or otherwise sense the same region, they submit *confirmation* or *rejection* transactions to the smart contract. These vehicles also rely on their own sensor inputs to verify the reported information. Multiple confirmation transactions strengthen the claim, while multiple rejection transactions may overturn it.

Step 5: Consensus Threshold. Once the threshold discussed in Section IV is reached, the pending state is resolved. The threshold is dynamically adjusted based on road type, event severity, and vehicle reputation. If consensus deems the newly reported data to be accurate, it is marked as *confirmed*. Otherwise, the entry is *rejected*.

Step 6: Data Finalization and Reward. In the event of a successful confirmation, the updated information is promoted to the *structured data layer* and disseminated to all vehicles' navigation systems. This ensures that other AVs immediately benefit from the new information, improving their route planning and operational safety. As an incentive, Vehicle **A**—the original proposer of the valid data—is awarded a token.

B. Modular Smart Contracts System

The proposed framework achieves flexibility and scalability by deploying three closely integrated smart contracts, each with a distinct but interlocking responsibility. As detailed in Algorithm 1, the *FilterContract* first receives every new data submission transmitted by a vehicle, performing checks on the JSON-encoded payload and verifying that no identical *pending* entry exists for the same event. When a new submission is found to be unique, the contract relays it to the *VotingContract* with *pending* status;

Once a proposal is marked as *pending*, the *VotingContract* takes over to manage crowd-sourced validation. Each vehicle that has relevant sensor data can cast a CONFIRM or REJECT vote. The contract keeps a running tally of both counts and, after each vote, recalculates a dynamic acceptance threshold according to the methodology presented in Section IV. This threshold denoted $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$, varies based on different factors such as the severity of the event, the criticality of the road segment, the elapsed time since the proposal was submitted, and the reputation of the proposer. In this way, the *VotingContract* can either finalize an outcome before the voting window concludes—triggered by immediate confirmation or rejection criteria—or wait until a predefined time limit or a minimum vote count is reached. Once a decision has been reached, the result is irrevocably recorded on-chain, ensuring transparency and accountability in the consensus process. The final module, the *TokenContract*, governs the system's incentive layer. Suppose the *VotingContract* signals that a proposal has been confirmed. In that case, the *TokenContract* mints one or more tokens in the name of the original proposer, thereby acknowledging a valid and beneficial data contribution to the network. Note that all reputation updates and flag management—incorporating the double-hit logic (discussed further below in Section IV-D) for handling consecutive negative proposals—are performed within the *VotingContract*, which decouples these operations from token management. The *TokenContract* further handles an array of token lifecycle operations, including transfer, balance tracking, and burn logic. This modular design, wherein the tokenomics are confined to a dedicated contract, allows for

Algorithm 1 Workflow for Distributed AV Data Sharing via Modular Smart Contracts

- 1: **Step 1: FilterContract - Initial Validation and Duplicate Checking**
- 2: Receive *txData* (e.g., infrastructure mismatch) and *vID* (vehicle pseudonym).
- 3: Perform basic checks on *txData* (required fields in JSON format).
- 4: Verify whether an identical *pending* entry already exists for the same issue.
- 5: **if** no matching entry is found **then**
- 6: Forward *txData* to *VotingContract* with *pending* status.
- 7: **else**
- 8: Convert this submission into a CONFIRM vote for the existing *pending* entry in *VotingContract*.
- 9: Do not create a new pending record.
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **Step 2: VotingContract - Consensus Mechanism**
- 12: Initialize vote counts for each *pending* proposal: *yesVotes* = 0, *noVotes* = 0.
- 13: **for** each vote received from vehicles **do**
- 14: **if** vote is CONFIRM **then**
- 15: Increment *yesVotes*.
- 16: **else if** vote is REJECT **then**
- 17: Increment *noVotes*.
- 18: **end if**
- 19: *Dynamic recalculation of $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$ and immediate check*
- 20: Check if *yesVotes* and *noVotes* trigger immediate approval or rejection.
- 21: **end for**
- 22: *At the end of the voting window or upon reaching the minimum required number of votes*
- 23: Check final consensus according to Section IV.
- 24: **if** proposal is approved **then**
- 25: Forward the approval result to *TokenContract*.
- 26: **else**
- 27: Mark the proposal as rejected.
- 28: **end if**
- 29: Emit an event indicating the outcome ("CONFIRMED" or "REJECTED").
- 30: Update *rep(vID)* and *flag(vID)* in accordance with Section IV-D.
- 31: **Step 3: TokenContract - Token Management**
- 32: **if** proposal is approved **then**
- 33: Mint a reward token to the proposer (*vID*).
- 34: Store the validated data in the *confirmed* repository.
- 35: **end if**
- 36: Handle all token lifecycle operations (e.g., emission, balance tracking, burn logic).

tailored governance and dynamic adjustments to reward policies without disrupting the consensus or filtering processes.

Together, these three smart contracts operate in unison to secure real-time data, validate its authenticity, and incentivize honest reporting. By cleanly separating the *filtering*, *consensus*, and *reward* functionalities, the architecture remains flexible to evolving requirements while preserving core trust assumptions.

C. Blockchain Platform

In order to maximize transparency, immutability, and cross-brand participation, our system leverages a blockchain:

- **public:** All transactions recorded on the blockchain ledger are openly readable, allowing stakeholders to audit the data flow and verify the integrity of reported events.
- **and permissionless:** Any entity may validate or produce blocks on the blockchain (depending on the adopted consensus mechanism) provided it adheres to the network's consensus rules. These rules define the proof-of-stake (or analogous) protocol that governs how new blocks are added to the chain.

Since vehicles remain pseudonymized via cryptographic addresses, privacy concerns are mitigated while retaining the benefits of a trustless, decentralized architecture. This permissionless approach fosters an open ecosystem where entities from multiple automotive manufacturers can seamlessly contribute to and benefit from the shared dataset by obviating the need for a central authority.

Although the proposed system already integrates a reputation model and dynamic thresholding, additional mechanisms could further refine both the consensus process and the reward structure. Under such a *dynamically weighted* scheme, submissions from reputable entities could reach an accelerated consensus on critical events while mitigating the influence of malicious actors. Similarly, the token issuance could be tied to contextual factors such as the severity or criticality of the event, effectively rewarding contributors based on the *quality* or *importance* of their reports.

Another promising avenue involves coupling vehicular identities to blockchain-based *Non-Fungible Tokens* (NFTs), as suggested by works like [4] leveraging zero-knowledge proofs (ZKPs) to allow vehicles to attest to their previous behavior or reputation level without revealing sensitive data or linking multiple contributions to a single, traceable real-world identity.

Furthermore, practical considerations for real-time, large-scale deployments underscore the need to minimize transaction costs and ensure network scalability. One viable solution is to adopt a high-throughput platform or a specialized *subnet* on public permissionless blockchains like Avalanche [12], or to employ a layer-two scaling solution on Ethereum [13]. By leveraging existing validator infrastructures, the system can dramatically reduce per-transaction fees and latencies, thereby enhancing both cost-effectiveness and responsiveness. Such an approach also preserves the trustless, decentralized nature of the network, which is essential for an open, multi-vendor ecosystem of autonomous vehicles.

D. Real-World Applications of the Reward Mechanism

The token-based reward mechanism introduced in our framework offers practical utilities beyond data contribution incentives, encouraging continuous engagement and fostering an ecosystem of mutual value creation among vehicles, users, and service providers. Specifically, tokens can be practically redeemed in multiple key scenarios within the autonomous vehicle ecosystem, such as:

- **Premium Data Access:** Vehicles holding tokens can utilize them to reduce or waive fees for accessing specialized or high-value data within the system, thus incentivizing continued participation.
- **Charging Discounts:** Electric and hybrid vehicles may redeem tokens to obtain discounts at charging stations, thereby reducing operational expenditures and promoting sustainable urban mobility.
- **Parking Fee Management:** Integration of tokens into urban parking systems allows users to conveniently pay

parking fees or receive price reductions, streamlining daily urban mobility.

- **Toll Payment Reduction:** Toll authorities can offer preferential toll rates or facilitate smoother billing transactions through token adoption, rewarding vehicles that actively contribute reliable road-condition data.

These practical applications, which can be later implemented, establish a continuous cycle of economic incentives, fostering widespread adoption by aligning individual benefits with collective improvements in road safety and efficiency.

IV. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION FOR DETERMINING THE DYNAMIC THRESHOLD

This section proposes a mathematical formulation for a dynamic threshold to efficiently manage the second smart contract described in Section III-B and Algorithm 1. The goal is to parameterize the various factors involved to allow urgent information to be accepted and transmitted to navigation systems in a timely manner. At the same time, it is crucial to prevent system manipulation by entities that repeatedly provide incorrect or fraudulent information, disfavoring them in the long term while accounting for possible detection and transmission errors.

We have introduced a reputation system for vehicles that transmit new information to the system; this parameter will play a role in modeling the dynamic acceptance threshold. However, we have chosen not to have the reputation affect the reaching of consensus (so individual vehicles will not have different weights when voting on whether a piece of information is correct or not). This ensures that the system is as distributed as possible and avoids single points of failure.

A. Basic Parameters and Notation

Let us define the following parameters and variables, which will be used throughout this section:

- $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, \dots, v_N\}$: the set of vehicles involved.
- $v_{\text{prop}}(i) \in \mathcal{V}$: the vehicle (proposer) that submits proposal i .
- $\text{sev}(i) \in [0, 1]$: the severity of the event reported by proposal i (e.g., road closure vs. incorrect speed limit).
- $\text{road}(i) \in [0, 1]$: the criticality of the road segment for proposal i (e.g., highway, urban, rural).
- $\Delta t_i \geq 0$: the time elapsed since the initial submission of proposal i , calculated as $\Delta t_i = \text{timestamp}_{\text{current}} - \text{timestamp}_{\text{start}}^{(i)}$.
- $\text{rep}(v) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$: the reputation score of vehicle v .
- $f(v) \in \{0, 1\}$: $f(v) = 1$ if a vehicle v is flagged in an *alert state* due to having recently submitted a rejected proposal.
- $\tau_{\text{base}} \geq 0$: the base threshold for approving a proposal with minimum severity and criticality.
- $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1, \gamma = 1, \lambda = 1$: coefficients for weighting the variables; we retain these coefficients for potential future adjustments.
- $T_{\text{min}} \geq 0, T_{\text{max}} \geq T_{\text{min}}$: global thresholds preventing the dynamic threshold from going below T_{min} or above T_{max} .
- $\text{timeWindow} > 0$: the maximum time the proposal must be confirmed or rejected.
- $k_{\text{min}} \geq 1$: the minimum number of votes required for a decision.
- $Y(i) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$: the number of CONFIRM / YES votes for proposal i .
- $N(i) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$: the number of REJECT / NO votes for proposal i .

B. Dynamic Acceptance Threshold

The dynamic acceptance threshold $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$ for proposal i is defined as:

$$T_{\text{dyn}}(i) = \text{clamp} \left[\tau_{\text{base}} + \alpha \text{sev}(i) + \beta \text{road}(i) - \gamma \ln(1 + \Delta t_i) - \lambda \text{rep}(v_{\text{prop}}(i)), T_{\text{min}}, T_{\text{max}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where:

- $\text{clamp}[x, a, b] = \min(\max(x, a), b)$ ensures that x is limited between a and b , preventing the threshold from becoming negative or excessively high.
- The parameters τ_{base} , α , β , γ , and λ are weighting coefficients that determine the influence of each factor on the dynamic threshold:
 - τ_{base} represents the base threshold for minimum severity and criticality;
 - α weighs the impact of the event severity $\text{sev}(i)$;
 - β weighs the impact of the road criticality $\text{road}(i)$.
 - γ weighs the influence of the elapsed time Δt_i (note that the natural logarithm ensures diminishing returns as time passes);
 - λ weighs the influence of the proposer's reputation $\text{rep}(v_{\text{prop}}(i))$.

In this initial application scenario we opted to initially set all coefficients equal to 1 ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = \lambda = \tau_{\text{base}} = 1$), deferring a more detailed parameter tuning to subsequent analyses. This allows us to assess the behavior of the normalized variables before applying different weights and to lay the groundwork for future multi-objective optimization as part of a simulation. Retaining the coefficients in the formula provides flexibility for potential adjustments based on empirical data or changing requirements.

Variables $\text{sev}(i)$ and $\text{road}(i)$ are normalized within the range $[0, 1]$ for consistency. The term Δt_i is measured in terms of the *number of blocks* emitted by the network, as it is the basic unit within the blockchain. Its scaling will depend on the selected blockchain platform.

The reputation $\text{rep}(v)$ is updated according to the rules specified in Section IV-D. The global thresholds T_{min} and T_{max} ensure that $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$ stays within acceptable bounds.

With this formulation, if the proposer's reputation is very high and/or a significant amount of time has passed (large Δt_i), the threshold lowers but never goes below T_{min} . Conversely, if the event's severity or the road segment's criticality is very high, the threshold cannot rise indefinitely due to T_{max} . Defining T_{min} and T_{max} based on preliminary tests or simulations to reflect real voting conditions and vehicle participation is advisable.

C. Voting Rules and Final Decision

Let $Y(i) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ and $N(i) \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ respectively denote the cumulative counts of approval (CONFIRM) and rejection (REJECT) votes for a pending proposal i . Let $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$ represent the dynamic validation threshold for proposal i , calculated according to the formula presented in Sec. IV-B. Additionally, let k_{min} represent the minimum number of votes necessary and timeWindow the maximum allowed voting duration.

The decision-making follows four phases:

- 1) **Immediate Confirmation Criterion:** A submitted data item is immediately accepted and finalized as **confirmed** if:

$$Y(i) \geq T_{\text{dyn}}(i) \quad \text{and} \quad Y(i) > N(i). \quad (2)$$

- 2) **Immediate Rejection Criterion:** Conversely, a proposal is immediately marked as **rejected** if either of the following conditions holds:

$$N(i) \geq T_{\text{dyn}}(i) \quad \text{or} \quad N(i) > Y(i). \quad (3)$$

- 3) **Final Resolution at Voting Closure:** If neither immediate confirmation nor immediate rejection criteria have been triggered by the end of the voting window (i.e., upon completion of time timeWindow or upon reaching the minimum vote requirement k_{min}), the final state of the proposal is decided according to the majority criterion:

$$\text{status}(i) = \begin{cases} \text{confirmed}, & Y(i) > N(i), \\ \text{rejected}, & Y(i) \leq N(i). \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

- 4) **Resolving Simultaneous Threshold Exceedance:** In scenarios where both approvals votes $Y(i)$ and rejection votes $N(i)$ concurrently cross the dynamic threshold $T_{\text{dyn}}(i)$ within the same time interval (e.g., within the same block of blockchain transactions), we deterministically resolve the ambiguity by evaluating the vote difference:

$$\text{status}(i) = \begin{cases} \text{confirmed} & \text{if } Y(i) - N(i) > 0, \\ \text{rejected}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

This deterministic voting scheme effectively prevents ambiguity and mitigates potential manipulation or exploitation of the voting system. The combination of dynamic thresholding, minimum vote counts, and defined timing windows guarantees reliable and timely decision-making, thereby enhancing overall data accuracy and consistency across automotive platforms.

D. Vehicle Reputation and Incentive Mechanism

To incentivize truthful data submission and build long-term vehicle collaboration, we implement a simple reputation model inspired by repeated-game frameworks [14]. Each vehicle $v \in \mathcal{V}$ maintains a reputation score $\text{rep}(v)$, initialized at a positive default value $\text{rep}_{\text{default}}$.

Our system adopts a *double-hit penalty* policy to balance fairness and robustness to errors. Specifically, when a vehicle proposes information that is subsequently rejected through the consensus procedure (Section IV), it does not suffer an immediate penalty, rather receiving a one-time binary warning flag $f(v)$. Only upon submitting two consecutive rejected proposals does the vehicle incur a reputation penalty Δ . Conversely, if previously decreased, a successfully confirmed contribution resets the flagged status and restores the vehicle's reputation score back to its default value.

These reputation adjustments have a twofold benefit: on the one hand, they discourage malicious and careless behavior while avoiding excessively penalizing occasional sensor inaccuracies or unavoidable false positives. This straightforward yet effective logic creates incentives for sustained collaborative participation by rewarding accurate, timely inputs and gently discouraging unreliable submissions.

In our implementation, the reputation updating logic remains encapsulated within the VotingContract (see Section III-B), thus clearly separating incentive management from foundational blockchain transactions.

V. BLOCKCHAIN SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To preliminarily validate the proposed blockchain architecture, we implemented and tested the modular smart contract system outlined in Algorithm 1, including the *FilterContract*, *VotingContract*, and *TokenContract*. We conducted experiments using the Hardhat Ethereum development environment, deploying Solidity-based smart contracts on an Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) emulator. All simulations were executed under a modest computer environment hosted by Ubuntu Linux 20.04 LTS system, powered by an Intel Core i3 processor and 8 GB of RAM. Additionally, to thoroughly emulate multiple interacting vehicles, the Hardhat environment was configured to feature an increased number of default accounts to carry out an extensive simulation. The simulation involved scripting in JavaScript to automate testing, thus ensuring repeatability and reproducibility. Additionally, several simulations were conducted by varying the initial configuration coefficients, thus paving the way for future optimization strategies. Notably, deploying the simulation on an EVM-based emulator allowed immediate transferability of validated smart contracts to any compatible Ethereum-like blockchain network, for instance, an Ethereum public testnet or Avalanche Fuji public testnet.

Specifically, our simulations successfully demonstrated on-chain dynamic threshold updates according to the mathematical formulation defined in Section IV. The tests confirmed the smart contracts' correct deployment, verified proper interaction among modules, and validated effective dynamic threshold recalculation upon varying event severities, road criticalities, elapsed blockchain time (simulated in emitted blocks), and vehicle reputation adjustments. Specifically, our tests highlighted an automatic threshold adjustment mechanism that increased the acceptance threshold for proposals submitted by a vehicle whose previous two submissions had been rejected, reflecting the corresponding decrease in its reputation score. Upon the acceptance of a subsequent (third) proposal originating from the same vehicle, the proposer's reputation was positively updated, effectively resulting in a lowered acceptance threshold and the successful allocation of the reward token. The code behind our tests is publicly available in our GitHub repository [15]. All experimentations and validations confirmed the practical feasibility and functionality of the designed system architecture.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel decentralized, blockchain-based framework designed to facilitate the secure and trustworthy exchange of sensor data among autonomous vehicles produced by diverse manufacturers. By employing a carefully designed modular smart contract architecture—comprising distinct filtering, consensus voting, and reward modules—we effectively address long-standing challenges related to interoperability, validation, and incentivization in Intelligent Transportation Systems. Specifically, our proposed approach leverages smart contracts, reputation-based voting mechanisms, and blockchain-based tokenization for economically incentivizing authenticated real-time data exchanges, thus significantly enhancing cross-brand cooperation.

The key of the proposed contribution is the *dynamic threshold model*, formulated to support real-time decision-making processes. The model incorporates multiple parameters, including event severity, road segment criticality, elapsed time, and submitter reputation, thereby enabling agile responses to critical infrastructural changes while mitigating adversarial input from

malicious entities. To rigorously evaluate our approach's effectiveness and practical performance, we conducted a simulation leveraging Hardhat, a widely adopted smart contract testing platform. The proposed architecture effectively aligns individual incentives with collective mobility objectives, thereby promoting safer, more reliable, and sustainable urban transportation.

Simulation results validate the efficacy and robustness of our proposed framework. Specifically, the implemented voting mechanism efficiently adapted the consensus conditions to varying contextual parameters, accurately adjusting acceptance thresholds. Furthermore, the smart contracts adequately managed proposal processing, validation, and reward token issuing, underscoring the system's operational feasibility and potential scalability.

Future work will implement realistic traffic simulations and optimize threshold coefficients through adaptive multi-objective optimization approaches.

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